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Luiz has developed a [policy brief](#) based on his own research which has had a [significant impact and reverberation](#) amongst a wide cohort of social actors in Brazil.



Whilst oftentimes social science research projects derive from contemporary social phenomena, there is still [an identified gap between academia and civil society](#), meaning that several research results do not reach key stakeholders beyond the academic world. It is already common knowledge amongst most PhD candidates and researchers at an early career stage that peer-reviewed publishing is of [paramount importance](#) for the advancement of the discipline and also to their own career advancement. Nevertheless, a considerable proportion of them still does not explore the full potential of disseminating their research findings also amongst the non-academic audience.

The key cohort of social actors such as, for instance, policymakers, leaders of non-governmental organisations, opinion makers and educators are oftentimes at the forefront of real social change that create an impact on people's lives. However, whilst peer-reviewed publishing encompasses the prominent channel to disseminate research findings and reach the academic community, they do not necessarily reach the mentioned key cohort of social actors. For this purpose, a concise and straight to the point [policy brief](#), written in a jargon-free language, clearly fulfils this need and bridge the gap between the academia and the civil society.

In addition to conveying social science research findings in a widely accessible language, the policy brief can contribute towards the establishment of a constructive and fruitful dialogue between the academia and the civil society. Furthermore, the key findings, data, and policy recommendations conveyed through the policy brief can support the future discussion, development and implementation of social policies and support initiatives and projects fostered by the [agents of social change](#).

There are several benefits of disseminating research results beyond the academia such as: a) providing civil society with well-thought evidence and data in regards to a given phenomenon that can contribute to the development of the means to tackle it; b) highlighting the relevance of a phenomenon that, eventually, not many social actors have already identified; c) democratic and open access to research results; and c) raising people's awareness about a new social trend worth attention and deeper reflection. Moreover, it also indirectly contributes towards raising the researcher's profile as an expert voice in the discipline.

Therefore, in conclusion, it is important first that PhD candidates and researchers at an early career stage engage in the work to identify the relevant cohort of key stakeholders in accordance with their own disciplines. Second, to keep in perspective the development of a well-thought, concise and accessible policy brief in order to disseminate their findings. Finally, to [actively promote](#) it amongst the key cohort of stakeholders making use of major social media platforms, distribution of press release, and publication of short non-academic articles in news outlets in order to spread the word about the document and foster civil society engagement with the research results.

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